

REVOLUTIONARY ETHICS - THE CORE VALUES IN PRESIDENT HO CHI MINH'S TESTAMENT

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Abstract: President Ho Chi Minh's Testament is a national treasure of Vietnam. This is a work that crystallizes his ideology, morality, style, and deep affection for the entire Party, the people and future generations. The content of Ho Chi Minh's Testament mentioned many important issues of the Vietnamese revolution, in which cultivating, training, and "imbued with revolutionary morality" is a core issue. Cultivating and practicing revolutionary morality according to Ho Chi Minh's Testament is not only an urgent issue for Vietnamese cadres, party members and people, but also universal in the world.

Keywords: Revolutionary ethics; value; President Ho Chi Minh's Testament.

I. INTRODUCTION

President Ho Chi Minh - The Hero of national liberation, The outstanding culturalist, The great teacher of the Vietnamese revolution, The genius leader of the Communist Party of Vietnam, The prominent revolutionary activist of the movements of communists and international workers. Before "passing away" to the eternal world, he left the Communist Party of Vietnam and the Vietnamese people a historical Testament. President Ho Chi Minh's Testament is not only the last words of advice, but also an extremely valuable spiritual legacy, crystallized in which the quintessence of revolutionary morality, soul, noble intellect, and His sentimental and immense spirit for the future generations. The contents of President Ho Chi Minh's Testament are the core issues and orientations for the development of the Vietnamese revolution today and in the future. The content of President Ho Chi Minh's Testament has always been thoroughly and effectively implemented by the Communist Party of Vietnam and the people.

II. THE WRITING PROCESS AND KEY CONTENTS OF THE TESTAMENT OF PRESIDENT HO CHI MINH

1. The writing process of President Ho Chi Minh's Testament

In 1965, President Ho Chi Minh wrote a Testament with the title " *Absolute Confidentiality* ". He wrote the Testament on the occasion of His 75th birthday when "the spirit is still clear-sighted, the body is still healthy" [6, p.611] but "was among a "rare" generation. He commented: "Who can guess how many years or how many months would I live and serve the Fatherland as well as serve the revolution? [6, p.611]. Therefore, He "... leave these words, just to summarize a few things. In case I go to see Mr. Marx, Mr. Lenin and other senior revolutionaries, the compatriots of the whole country and comrades in the Party will not be surprised" [6, p.611]. The Testament was dated May 15, 1965, three pages long, typed by himself, signed by himself and witnessed by comrade Le Duan, the First Secretary of the Central Committee at that time.

In 1966, President Ho Chi Minh added more content to the section on the practice of broad democracy, self-criticism and criticism within the Party, emphasizing: "There must be comrades-in-arms and mutual affection" [6, p.611].

In 1967, President Ho Chi Minh reviewed the testament, but he did not change anything.

In 1968, President Ho Chi Minh wrote an additional section into the Testament with six handwritten pages referring to personal affairs; what to do after the war of resistance against the US to save the country was completely victorious.

On May 10, 1969, President Ho Chi Minh wrote an additional section into the Testament, including a handwritten page affirming that the resistance war against the US and national salvation would definitely be victorious; the intentions He would carry out after the revolution succeeded; on the reasons for writing the Testament.

Thus, President Ho Chi Minh's Testament was written, revised and completed within a period of four years. That shows how much enthusiasm, intellect, spirit, immense affection and prudence and special care He devoted to writing the final instructions to leave the Communist Party of Vietnam and future generations to come.

2. The core content of the Testament

2.1. First of all, let's give our precious words to the Party

In His Testament, President Ho Chi Minh wrote "First of all, let's give our precious words to the Party". When referring to the Party, he focused on the following contents:

Firstly, President Ho Chi Minh paid special attention to preserving and consolidating solidarity and unanimity within the Party. He affirmed: "Solidarity is an extremely precious tradition of the Party and of our people. Comrades from the Central Committee to the cell branches need to preserve the unity and consensus of the Party like preserving the pupils of their eyes" [6, p.611]. According to Him, "In the Party, practicing democracy widely, regularly and seriously self-criticism and criticism is the best way to strengthen and develop solidarity and unanimity within the Party." [6, p.611]. "There must be comrades-in-arms and mutual affection" [6, p.611].

Second, He focused on affirming the improvement and training of revolutionary morality of cadres and party members. He affirmed: "Our Party is a ruling Party. Each party member and cadre must be truly imbued with *revolutionary morality*, thrift, integrity, fairness, and impartiality. We must keep our Party pure and worthy of being the leader and faithful servant of the people" [6, pp.611-612].

Third, He focused on reorganizing the Party. He advised: "In my opinion, the first thing to do is to reorganize the Party, so that each Party member, each union member, and each cell will make every effort to fulfill the tasks assigned to them by the Party wholeheartedly to serve the people. If we can do that, then no matter how great the work, how difficult it is, we will definitely win" [6, p.616]. The reason is that President Ho Chi Minh understands that the Party plays a very important role: "The Party has a strong revolution to succeed, just like only when the helmsman has a firm hold on the boat can it run smoothly" [2, p.289]. Therefore, the construction and rectification of the Party is the law of existence and development of the Party. As He once warned: "One people, one party and each person, yesterday was great, used to have great attraction, does not mean that today and tomorrow will still be loved and praised by everyone, if hearts are not pure anymore, if they fall into individualism" [6, p.672].

Fourth, fostering the revolutionary generation for the next generations. He considered it "a very important and vital duty". During his career of revolutionary activities, President Ho Chi Minh always cared about the cause of "planting people", taking care of building revolutionary forces. Therefore, in His *Testament*, He instructed the whole Party to always keep in mind that: "Our union members and youth are generally good, they are all willing to volunteer, not afraid of difficulties, and have the will to advance. The Party needs to take care of them in educating them on revolutionary morality, training them to be heirs to build socialism both "pink" and "specialized" [6, p.612].

Fifth, "continuously improving people's living standards". This is the red thread that runs through President Ho Chi Minh's goals and ideals of revolutionary activities. He went out to find a way to save the country in order to liberate the nation, bringing prosperity, freedom and happiness to the people. He had the ultimate desire to make the country completely independent, our people completely free, all the compatriots have food, clothing, everyone can study. Therefore, in His Testament, He advised the Party: "The Party needs to have a good plan for economic and cultural development, in order to constantly improve people's lives" [6, p.612].

2.2. The first duty is jobs for people

In His Testament, President Ho Chi Minh not only took care of the construction and rectification of the Party, but also deeply cared about people. In the supplementary Testament in May of 1968, President Ho Chi Minh wrote: "The first duty is jobs for people". From his immense compassion, President Ho Chi Minh always took special care of people. In his Testament, he raised extremely comprehensive issues but also very complete, detailed work to be done: For those who have bravely sacrificed a part of their blood; for the martyrs, each locality; for parents, wives and children (of war invalids and martyrs) who lack labor capacity and are in need; young soldiers in the people's armed forces and young volunteers; for women; for the victims of the old social system; for farmers.

With special concerns to the people, President Ho Chi Minh advised: "Here we talk about the plan to rebuild cities and villages more beautiful and dignified than before the war. Restoring and expanding economic sectors. Developing hygiene and medical work. Modifying the education regime to suit the people's new circumstances, such as developing schools with half day of study and half day of work. Defense consolidating. Preparing everything for the unification of the Fatherland..." [6, p.617]. According to President Ho Chi Minh: "The above work is huge, heavy, and complicated, but also very glorious. This is a fight against the old, the bad, to create the new, the good. In order to gain victory in this huge battle, it is necessary to mobilize the whole people, organize and educate the whole people, relying on the great force of the whole people" [6, p.617].

That concern lies in President Ho Chi Minh's consistent strategy towards people. People are both the goal and the driving force of the revolution. This is a view that shows the superiority of the social system chosen and built by the Party, President Ho Chi Minh and the Vietnamese people.

2.3. About the resistance war against US imperialism

In His Testament, President Ho Chi Minh accurately predicted the resistance war against the US to save the country, despite hardships and many sacrifices, but certain victory.

In 1965, Ho Chi Minh predicted: "The resistance war against the US will probably last for several more years. Our compatriots may have to make many sacrifices of many people. Anyway, we must be determined to fight the American aggressor to complete victory.

The mountains are still here, the country is still here, the people are still here,

Defeat the American invaders, we will rebuild the country ten times richer than today!

No matter how difficult it was, our people would definitely win. The American empire must get out of our country. Our country would certainly unify. The people of the South and the North will definitely gather in one house. Our country would have the great honor of being a small country that has heroically defeated two big empires - France and America; and have made a worthy contribution to the national liberation movement" [6, p.612].

On May 10, 1969, He edited and continued to refer to the resistance war against the US, He wrote: "Our people's war against the US and national salvation, although we have to go through more hardships and sacrifices, but definitely completely victorious. That is a sure thing" [6, p.618].

President Ho Chi Minh's instructions in His Testament about the resistance war against the US and save the country are both accurate predictions about the outcome of the war; just demonstrated the determination and iron will of the Vietnamese people to liberate the nation and unify the country in the spirit of: "Nothing is more precious than independence and freedom"; both a source of encouragement and great spiritual encouragement for the whole nation to stand up to fight against the US and save the country.

2.4. About the international communist movement

President Ho Chi Minh is the great leader of the Vietnamese revolution, as well as the eminent leader of the international communist movement. During his life of revolutionary activities, He made a lot of great contributions to the development of the international communist movement. He always upheld the pure and faithful proletarian international spirit on the basis of Marxism-Leninism, rationality and love. He attached great importance to promoting the spirit of solidarity and friendship between brotherly parties, brother countries, and the democratic and progressive movement in the world; affirming that the Vietnamese revolution was a part of the world revolution; focusing on combining the strength of the

nation with the strength of the times. For that reason, in His Testament, He expressed His anguish about the discord of the international communist and workers' movements. He mentioned: "As a person who serve the revolution lifelong, the more proud I am of the growth of the international communist and workers' movements, the more heartbroken I am because of the current discord between the brother party!" [6, p.613]. He instructed the Communist Party of Vietnam to: "... make every effort to work and make an effective contribution to restoring the unity of the fraternal parties on the basis of Marxism-Leninism and proletarian internationalism, has a good reason." [6, p.613]. At the same time, He also expressed His strong belief: "I am convinced that brotherly parties and brother countries will definitely have to unite" [6, p.613].

2.5. About personal affairs and wishes before passing away

From his dedication in his revolutionary activities, President Ho Chi Minh summed up: "All my life I wholeheartedly serve the Fatherland, the revolution, and the people. Now, even though I have to leave this world, I have no regrets, only regret that I can't serve longer and more" [6, p.615]. He advised: "After I have passed away, don't hold a grand funeral, so as not to waste people's time and money" [6, p.615]. He proposed: "I request that my body be burned, that is, 'cremated'. I hope that the "cremation" method will be popular in the future. Because of that, for people who live well in terms of hygiene, they do not waste land. When we have a lot of electricity, the "electric burial" is better" [6, p.615]. He wished: "The ashes are divided into 3 parts and put in 3 crockery boxes. A box for the North. One box for Central. One box for the South. People in each region should choose a hill to bury the ash box. On the grave, there should be no bronze steles and statues, but a simple, spacious, solid and cool house should be built, so that visitors can have a place to rest" [6, p.615].

President Ho Chi Minh said a very emotional farewell, expressing His immense love. He wrote: "Finally, I leave a lot of love for the whole people, the whole Party, the whole army, the young people and children. I also extend my cordial greetings to comrades, friends, and international youth and children" [6, p.613].

In the last line of the Testament, He wrote a very noble last wish, showing His special concern for the development of the Party, nation and revolution of Vietnam: "My last wish. The whole Party and people of our country unite to strive to build a peaceful, united, independent, democratic and strong Vietnam, and make a worthy contribution to the world revolutionary cause. [6, p.614].

III. REVOLUTIONARY ETHICS - VALUE, MEANING

Reading, researching and understanding President Ho Chi Minh's Testament shows that it contains the strategic ideas of the genius revolutionary leader. One of the contents reflected by people with a condensed statement is: "Improve revolutionary morality". In terms of form, it is reflected briefly and succinctly, but it is an issue of great value and meaning, an issue that President Ho Chi Minh cared about improving and training throughout his life. Practice shows that the cultivation, training and imbuing of revolutionary morality according to President Ho Chi Minh's testament have great value and significance. That is shown:

First, morality is the root of the revolutionary cadre. Morality is the original criterion of a person. Morality is likened to a river with a source, a tree with a root. Heaven has four seasons: Spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter. Earth has four directions: East, West, South, and North. Humans have the four virtues of Need, Integrity, Integrity, and Righteousness. Therefore, the cultivation and training of revolutionary morality is not only valuable and meaningful to each cadre, party member and people of Vietnam, but also has universal value around the world.

Second, revolutionary morality is the driving force and source of all success of the revolution. President Ho Chi Minh said that making a revolution to renovate the old society and build a better new society is an extremely glorious job but also very heavy, arduous and long-lasting, so it must be Revolutionary ethics as the new foundation can succeed. He wrote: "It is only with strength that you can carry a burden and go far. The revolutionary must have revolutionary morality as the foundation to fulfill the glorious revolutionary task" [5, p.601].

Thirdly, morality is also the spiritual foundation, the root of bravery of cadres and revolutionaries. He wrote: "Having revolutionary morality, when facing advantages and successes, they still maintain the spirit of hardship, simplicity, humility, "worry before the world, happy after the world"; take care of completing the task well, not trumpet in terms of enjoyment; no justice, no bureaucracy, no arrogance, no corruption. It is also an expression of revolutionary morality" [5, p.603].

Fourth, revolutionary morality is the basis and foundation for leading the people. President Ho Chi Minh understood: "... the peoples of the East are full of emotions, and for them a vital example is worth more than a hundred propaganda speeches" [1, p.284]. From there, He came to affirm: "Revolutionaries must have morality, without morality, no matter how talented they are, they cannot lead the people. Because wanting to liberate the nation and liberate the human race is a big job, but you have no morals, no foundation, you are corrupt and evil yourself, what else can you do?" [3, pp.292-293].

Fifth, revolutionary morality is the factor that creates the attractiveness of socialism. According to President Ho Chi Minh, the attraction of socialism is not in the lofty ideals, in the abundant material living standards, in the liberated thought, but first in the moral values. noble virtue in the qualities of elite communists, by their example of life and actions, fighting for that ideal to become reality. He affirmed: "In front of the masses, it is not that we write on our foreheads the word 'communist' that we are loved by them. The masses only love people with moral character. To guide the people, we must set a standard for others to imitate" [4, p.16].

IV. CONCLUDE

Revolutionary ethics is one of the content throughout Ho Chi Minh's thought. In His work Revolutionary Road, He focused on generalizing issues related to the status of a revolutionary. After that, in many speeches and articles, President Ho Chi Minh mentioned the role, content, motto and method of building revolutionary morality associated with the struggle against individualism. In His Testament, He raised many important issues of the Vietnamese revolution, in which He asked cadres and party members to "be imbued with revolutionary morality". This is valuable content, extremely deep meaning, great. The cultivation and training of revolutionary morality according to President Ho Chi Minh's testament is a necessary and urgent matter for every Vietnamese cadre, party member and people, but also a matter of great value to the people of Vietnam universally and around the world.

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